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A Peer Reviewed (Refereed) International Journal**Article Information**Received: 27th Feb, 2025Accepted: 28th Feb, 2025Published: 25th April, 2025**MIGRATION AND HUMAN RESOURCE DEPLETION/ BRAIN DRAIN;
A SCORE FOR NATION DEVELOPMENT****Dr. Duezeh, Emmanuel Afamefuna**Department of Public Administration Faculty of Management Sciences Nnamdi Azikiwe
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ABSTRACT

With hindsight, insight and foresight of the Nigeria history and development, Critical observation across human existence has shown that poor development of countries had being linked to the migration of human resources to countries. Human migration, being the movement by people from one place to another with the intention of settling temporarily or permanently in the new location for better standard of living. Migration can be voluntary or involuntary. Involuntary migration includes the slave trade, trafficking in human beings and ethnic cleansing. Young, well-educated, healthy individuals are most likely to migrate, especially in pursuit of higher education and economic improvement. Migration and Human resource Depletion/Brain-dain is a steady phenomenon causing downs instead of ups to the development of a country especially where it is in top gear. The current exodus of people both young and old from Nigeria to other developing and developed countries for greener pastures have become a teething problems and a torn in the fresh of the country minding that such migration will definitely shot down the developmental strides of the Country. The human migration especial the professionals in different areas of life called brain drain is likened to social environment which is often considered to be a key reason for this population shift. In source countries, lack of opportunities, Government misplaced primacy, political instability or oppression, economic depression, health risks and more contribute to human capital flight/human resource depletion/ brain drain. The main thrust of this research work is to investigate the causes of the age-bending phenomenon, its effect and proffer possible solutions to the effect. The related literature was secondarily revealed. The study recommended countries to usually offer rich opportunities, political stability and freedom, industrialization winnings, a developed economy and better living conditions that attract talents.

Keywords: Migration, Human Resource depletion, Brain-drain, countries, phenomenon**INTRODUCTION**

In our present-day Nigeria, the state of socio-economic development dictates the necessity to harness all our resources for the betterment of our people. The situation of everyday living in Nigeria needs no further documentation; we all know that it is very bad when compared with that of advanced countries of Western Europe and North America. The implications for the

socioeconomic welfare of our people will be invaluable even if fifty percent of Nigerian professionals currently abroad which is called “*brain drain*”, especially medical doctors, were back working and living in Nigeria. Standard dictionary defines brain drain “as the loss of skilled intellectual and technical labour through the movement of such labour to more favourable geographic, economic, or professional environ, depletion or loss of intellectual and technical personnel, a gradual depletion of energy or resources; a drain of young talent by emigration”

By way of explanation, brain drain is a popular euphemism for the phenomenon, whereby a significantly large number of highly skilled individuals leave a particular geographical area called ‘*migration*’, usually their nations of origin, for other nations over a comparatively short period of time because of a variety of reasons. Consequently, the areas from where they departed are impoverished one way or the other. Essentially their nations of origin are denied the services and expertise they would have otherwise provided. This phenomenon would resonate with the Nigerian society. It has its hands in the deteriorating situation of our institutions of higher learning; it is visible in our major industries. The private sector is denied the experience such people would have brought to bear on the economy. The root cause of brain drain in Nigeria lies with our successive leaderships and governments that have demonstrated, very convincingly, that the interest of Nigeria and its citizens were never their priority. They relentlessly pursued their own agenda. However, the bottom line surmised from the views of most Nigerians is that corruption is a problem that has to be rooted out. In Nigeria another major cause of corruption is ethnicity called tribalism in Nigeria. Friends and kinsmen seeking favor from officials may impose difficult strains on the ethical disposition of the official. Many kinsmen may see a government official as holding necessary avenues for their personal survival or gain (Eccker, 1981p.98).

It is doubtful if one can really discuss the issue of brain drain without making some reference to patriotism. Patriotism, that is, love and devotion to one’s country cannot be absolute, quite often it is situated in an identifiable social context. Is patriotism present in deficient proportion in Nigerians working and living in advanced countries? Absolutely not, however, it may be so if patriotism is defined in a narrow sense and out of context with prevailing conditions in Nigeria. Otherwise how can one explain the apparent complacency of Nigerian professionals abroad when they keep on toiling day and night to oil the machine of development and advancement of the industrialized and advanced economies of Western Europe and North America to the detriment of their home countries?

There are various reasons why professionals, for example, doctors decide to live and work in developed world. Irrespective of the propriety of such decisions the current situation is that the issue should be addressed at the highest level of government. One can pontificate a lot about the root causes of brain-drain. I think it is high time the issue was brought to the fore, It would seem to me that instead of a great deal of pledging or in some cases giving millions of dollars to African nations in the form of Aid ,the developed world should work with African nations to honestly address the root causes of what make their philanthropy inevitable. In a very practical way western governments can work with national governments of Africa on the active encouragement of the reversal of brain-drain. The blame for brain drain lies squarely with the various governments that have ruled the developing nations of Africa. Those governments, through their ineptitude and lack of vision, have turned their populations with productive capacities to willing sophisticated slaves in foreign lands. Nevertheless, a modern practical approach to leadership and relationships has gradually taken a prominent role in the political process. The necessity for practical inter-dependence and cooperation is at the forefront of yearnings for good governance in the country (“*South Elevation: Breaking Views: Nigeria: Corruption Perception Index*”. Retrieved 2 June 2018). It is shameful to see regularly on the television the tell-tale signs of economic and administrative poverties of the developing nations.

It is not in the interest of developing nations that this trend should continue unabated. The idea of free, trade globalization and free movement of labour would find new meanings with the apologists of brain drain. For the Nigerian people the impact of brain drain is too costly and should no longer be ignored. The improvement to the life of the nation and that of ordinary Nigerians would increase exponentially if our drained manpower is back home where it rightly belongs. There is need to bring the issue of brain drain to national and international consciousness, we have ignored it for too long and much to our own peril. The Federal government and the national assemblies must discuss it. Nigeria deserves the establishment of a commission to look into the magnitude of the problems and proffer solutions. A very practicable way of addressing it is for Nigerian governments – local, state and Federal to actively address the issue. The details of this can be worked out by the commission.

1.2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEMS

The current rate of brain drain in Nigeria is mostly a function of the present economic depression in Nigeria – a depression caused by some ignorant, selfish, inconsiderate, mindless looters of Nigerian treasury. These sadists, often called leaders, have looted (and continue to loot) Nigerian coffer only to pile up the contents in their private foreign bank accounts. Consequently, greener pastures i.e., jobs are created abroad while Nigeria has no pasture. At the 10th Annual Conference of the Nigerian People and Organizations (CONPO), held in Atlanta, Sept. 17-20, 1998, that Nigeria has the greatest number of educated foreigners in the US. This is a clear evidence of brain drain in Nigeria. Of course, evidence of brain drain in Nigeria can also be seen at the social gatherings of Nigerians in the US. Particularly noticeable at these gatherings is the growing population of Nigerians born in the US. Any time one thinks of this population, one is confronted with a very disturbing question: If the parents of these youths cannot live in Nigeria, is there a hope that these youths born and bred in America will live in Nigeria? Put differently, why is Nigerian brain being drained? How can Nigeria revert this tragic trend, and retain her brains as she used to do in late 70s and early 80s? Therefore, being deprived of a greener pasture, coupled with the desperate need to feed their families and relatives, especially those at home, some Nigerian brains are essentially forced to travel and remain abroad. So, when it was revealed at the CONPO conference (see above) that Nigerians sent home \$168 million in 1997 through Western Union, one will not totally be surprised. An attempt is made here to address these questions.

But, while the search for greener pasture explains, in part, the current brain drains in Nigeria, there is no doubt that brain drain has become a crucial part of the problems of development in Nigeria.

An attempt is made here to address these questions. Today, there are many Nigerian bankers, business managers, computer scientists, pharmacists, engineers, journalists, lawyers, medical doctors, nurses, pharmacists, Administrators, professors, and scientists in the West. These educated Nigerians abroad are basically making little or no contribution towards the task of developing Nigeria; the West is mostly the beneficiary of their talents. As it stands now, the West is not only enjoying the money stolen from Nigeria by those sadists, it is also milking Nigerian human resources. Definitely, something must be done to stop brain drain and its associated problems of development in Nigeria. In Bedford (2018), Nigerians must realize that brain drain cannot be solved with brain drain. Put differently, problems are not solved when people run away from them; problems are solved only when people take the responsibility for those problems. Simply put, Nigeria's problems cannot be solved by mass exodus of Nigerian brains.

Again, the mentality of some Nigerians that "Nigeria's problems are beyond solution" is entirely incorrect. This mentality should be rejected because it is not serving any useful purpose. Besides,

Nigeria's problems are man-made, i.e., there are no acute natural disasters in Nigeria, and so they can be corrected by man. It is the bounded duty of the educated men and women of any polity to address their problems no matter how big or complicated. Educated Nigerians should not be different.

(<http://www.angelfire.com/tx/bumez><http://www.geocities.com/CapitolHill/4172>)

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Accordingly, the general objective of the study is to examine the issue of migration and brain drain. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Why Nigeria brain being drain
- ii. How can Nigeria revert this tragic trends of brain drain
- iii. Make recommendations on the way forward for the embattled country.

1.4 THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

Theoretical frame work of the study is Two Factor Theory by Frederick Herzberg. The theory postural in a practical ways and means through which an employees can be kept in a named organization or Country while contributing to the progress of the Organization or the Country without thinking migration to another Country. In Herzberg, (2005pp.61-74), this theory, also called the Motivation-Hygiene Theory or the dual-factor theory, was penned by Frederick Herzberg in 1959. This American psychologist, who was very interested in people's motivation and job satisfaction, came up with the theory. He conducted his research by asking a group of people about their good and bad experiences at work. He was surprised that the group answered questions about their good experiences very differently from the ones about their bad experiences.

Based on this, he developed the theory that people's job satisfaction depends on two kinds of factors. Factors for satisfaction (motivators/satisfiers) and factors for dissatisfaction (hygiene factors/ dissatisfiers).

Performance, recognition, job status, responsibility and opportunities for growth all fall under motivators/ satisfiers.

Hygiene factors/dissatisfiers are about salary, secondary working conditions, the relationship with colleagues, physical work place and the relationship between supervisor and employee.

In his theory, Herzberg claims these factors function on the same plane. In other words, satisfaction and dissatisfaction aren't polar opposites. Taking away an employee's dissatisfaction – for example by offering a higher salary – doesn't necessarily mean the employee will then be satisfied. The employee is just no longer dissatisfied.

4 different combinations can exist at work:

1: High hygiene and high motivation

This is the ideal situation. Employees are very motivated and barely have any complaints.

2: High hygiene and low motivation

Employees have few complaints, but they're not really motivated, they see their work simply as a pay check.

3: Low hygiene and high motivation

Employees are motivated, their job is challenging, but they have complaints about salary or work conditions.

4: Low hygiene and low motivation

This is the worst possible situation; employees are not motivated and have a lot of complaints.

KITA

Adjusting the hygiene factors, also called the **KITA** (Kick in the Ass) factors by Herzberg, often have a short-term effect that doesn't last very long. Changing the motivation factors on the other hand often has a more lasting, long-term effect on employee performance.

1.4.1 How to apply the Two Factor Theory?

Organisations and their managers want teams with the best possible performance. But how do you motivate that team? There's not much point in motivating employees if the hygiene factors aren't taken care of. Motivating people really works when the things that bother them – the things they complain about -disappear.

Take away the dissatisfaction

To do this, it's important to figure out all the important factors first. What are the complaints about, what's going on, how do the employees interact with each other? Generally speaking, the following aspects are important:

- Work on the bureaucracy within the organisation
- Make sure there's supportive and effective supervision
- Create a work environment where all employees are respected
- Pay an honest salary
- Make sure all employees do worthwhile work to build up the status of their functions
- Give job guarantees

When the dissatisfaction is taken away, the organisation can focus on motivating its employees effectively.

Create conditions for satisfaction

For motivation within the organisation, think about:

- Creating conditions for good performance
- Appreciating your employees' contributions
- Tailoring the work to your employees' talents and abilities
- Giving each team as much responsibility as possible
- Offering opportunities for growth within the organisation
- Offering training and development opportunities

Organisations are prone to take Kick In The Ass measures in the short term, because they don't affect the organisational structure that much. A higher salary, better work conditions etc. Measures for motivation require bigger investments and changes to the organisational culture, Kuijk, A. (2018), *Two Factor Theory by Frederick Herzberg*. Retrieved [insert date] from ToolsHero: <https://www.toolshero.com/management/two-factor-theory-herzberg/>.

1.4.2 SUMMARY OF THE TWO FACTOR THEORY BY HERZBERG

The Two Factor Theory by Herzberg is a theory about motivation of employees. The Two Factor Theory assumes on the one hand, that employees can be dissatisfied with their jobs. This often has something to do with so-called hygiene factors, such as salary and work conditions. On the other hand, employees' satisfaction has to do with so-called motivation factors. These factors have to do with development opportunities, responsibility and appreciation.

Herzberg claims these factors exist side by side. Taking away the dissatisfaction factors doesn't necessarily mean employees will be satisfied. To motivate a team using motivation factors, the hygiene factors need to be taken care of first.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The significance of this study can be discussed under empirical and theoretical perspectives, from the empirical point of view; the study is a good guide to practicing administrators and administrative planners. The recommendations of this study could provide a sound basis for decision making as regards industrialization, employability, training and development workers, payment of salaries as at when due and highly programmed retirement benefits.

The study will be useful to the Nigerian Law Makers to understand the important of putting at a halt the dreaded brain drain causes and thereby appreciate the need for the implementation of the recommendations. Theoretically, the study will add to the existing body of qualitative knowledge on the issue and also serve as a source of knowledge retraces and point of building block for further researchers in the subject area.

1.6 METHODOLOGY

Sequel to the extant literature on the Migration and human resource depletion/ brain drain score for nation development as well as the theoretical framework, with the clear guide of the objectives, the related literature was revealed using secondary source of data.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL ISSUES

2.1 Human Migration

Human migration is the movement by people from one place to another with the intentions of settling temporarily or permanently in the new location. In (Ibe, 2016p.77), the movement is often over long distances and from one country to another, but internal migration is also possible; indeed, this is the dominant form globally. Migration may be individuals, family units or in large groups. According to Kelber (2012p.81), stated that, human migration, being the movement by people from one place to another with the intention of settling temporarily or permanently in the new location, typically involves movements over long distances and from one country or region to another. Migration can be voluntary or involuntary. Involuntary migration includes the slave trade, trafficking in human beings and ethnic cleansing while voluntary includes marriage, employment and other divine vocations. In the work of Olisa (1999p.45), human migration is one of the oldest civilizational processes, man has been moving from one place to another since the dawn of time. Reasons for migration vary greatly, but the overall purpose of the process is for people to move and settle in a better geographical location. The official so to say definition of human migration is the permanent change of residence of an individual or group. However, migration doesn't cover moves such as nomadism, migrant labour and tourism which are only temporary or transitory in nature. Migration should not be confused with immigration or emigrations, which are two distinctly different processes. Migration is something people have been doing for thousands of years. Throughout the ages history has witnessed a number of so-called great migrations, the results of which can still be seen today.

This movement of people often causes dangers to the growth and development of a Nation all ramifications be it health, politics, trade, agriculture, power and more lead to what is called *brain drain or human flight*.

Human capital flight refers to the emigration of highly skilled or well-educated individuals. The net benefits of human capital flight for the sending country are sometimes referred to as a "brain gain" whereas the net costs are sometimes referred to as a "brain drain".

Research shows that there are significant economic benefits of human capital flight both for the migrants themselves and those who remain in the country of origin. It has been found that emigration of skilled individuals to the developing world contributes to greater education and innovation in the developing world. Research also suggests that emigration, remittances and return migration can have a positive impact on democratization and the quality political institutions in the country of origin. Claims of a "brain drain" remain largely unsupported in academic research, with some scholars describing it as a "myth".

2.2 TYPES OF HUMAN MIGRATION

There are many factors which help put human migration into different types or categories. Some scientists break down migration into more subcategories, based on specific factors. Others prefer to keep migration explanations as simple as possible. So, what types of migration are there? First of all, there are:

- **Internal migration** – this is the movement of people from one region of a sovereign country to another, for instance rural to city migration. Internal migration is totally different to external migration.
- **External migration** – this is the movement of people and families from one country to another. Migrating externally can be regional where people move to a country nearby, or

continental and transcontinental where people travel over large distances to settle in another continent altogether.

There are also two other types of human migration known as voluntary and forced migration. Their names are rather self-explanatory, but let's elaborate regardless:

- **Voluntary migration**– this could be either internal or external, voluntary migration is movement of people under their own will, in search of better economic and housing opportunities.
- **Forced migration** – this is not a very nice way to move countries; forced migration is usually the expulsion of individuals by the government during state of war or other political upheaval. Individuals forced into migration (external or internal) could be transported out of the country in exile, or as prisoners or slaves. Science puts an intermediate category of migration between voluntary and forced, and that is migration caused by famine, natural disaster or fleeing war. A community authority may decide to forcefully move some of their idle subjects out the community to enable them find succours for themselves with no intention to hurt them but to make them become operational and productivity in their life and to come back home like ten or fifteen years of sojourns.

2.3 BRAIN DRAIN, THE CAUSES AND EFFECTS

The highest challenges facing any developing country of this century is making use of her skilled manpower, and ensuring that their teeming graduates are employed and keep them within their country of origin to tap from their God giving talents and skilled. The steady ups and downs in the most developing countries were as a result of the hyper corruption tendencies. Corruption is Nigeria's biggest challenge. It is clear to every citizen that the level of corruption in the country is high. It's found in every sector of society. Be it a small or big sector, there is every possibility of observing corrupt practices when critically examined. Corruption is the dishonest or fraudulent conduct by those in power, typically involving bribery. It is the illegitimate use of power to benefit a private interest (Morris 1991). Corruption is the giving of a bribe to an official so that the truth will not be told. It involves the embezzlement of public fund for personal use and any act which is considered to be criminal act according to the law of a particular society. Corruption is potent cancer that has mercilessly eaten Nigeria to a state of stupor-Professor Peter U. Nwangwu.

2.4 Causes of Corruption

A number of things cause corruption, and among them are:

- Greed
- Poor youth empowerment
- Poverty
- Unemployment

Greed

Greed has caused a lot of crises in the world, including in Nigeria. It is because of greed that political leaders embezzle from the funds they are supposed to use for national development for their own selfish needs.

Poor Youth Empowerment

Poor moral youth empowerment is a contributor to corruption. Internet fraud, sexual harassment by male CEOs, and other bad acts are because Nigerians lack understanding on the importance of youth empowerment. When parents and governments empower youths both financially and morally, the level of corruption among them will diminish.

Poverty

According to international standards of poverty, a person is said to be poor when he lives under \$1.25 (₦210, though it varies) per day. There are many poor people in Nigeria, and poverty pushes them into corruption. According to World Bank Group, in 2004, 63.1% of Nigerians were poor. The poverty level increased in 2010. In 2010, 68% of the Nigerian population were estimated to be poor. A person can take bribes to commit crime because he is poor. It is one of the reasons why the poor youths in the country collect bribes to work as thugs for Nigerian politicians.

Unemployment

Unemployment is one of the major challenges in Nigeria and does not need much explanation because it has broken the hearts of many citizens. People are pushed into corrupt practice because of high unemployment. An unemployed citizen can indulge in corruption to make money and live better.

The youths, fathers and mothers are seriously lamenting on the negative impact of unemployment in their lives. Some said that it is better for death to come and take their lives than suffering under the torment of unemployment challenge in the country. Words cannot explain the level of punishment the citizens of this country are as a result of this menace.

2.5 EFFECTS OF CORRUPTION

The negative consequences of corruption are many, and among them are:

- Poor investment
- Rise in poverty
- Poor national development
- National crises

Poor Investment

Unemployment in Nigeria would have been eradicated to some extent if only investors were attracted to it. Companies that would have invested in Nigeria are afraid because they do not know if the corrupt practice will ruin their industries in time. Because of this, they refuse to invest in Nigeria.

Rise in Poverty

When the heads of public service are busy laundering the money that is supposed to be used to create employment for the masses and reduce poverty, what happens is that there will be a rise in the poverty level of the country. Just like the rise in poverty as statistically shown between 2004 and 2008. Since the government is selfish and does not want to help the poor, poverty continues to rise in Nigeria.

Poor National Development

Any country with high corruption is likely to experience developmental bankruptcy. A situation where some CEOs indulge in corrupt practices to make their money means that economic development will suffer. When Nigerians keep on shifting the country's currency to foreign countries, there will be less economic development in Nigeria.

National Crises

So many crises in Nigeria today are as a result of corruption. The insecurity in Nigeria brought about by Boko Haram is a consequence of corruption. Corrupt politicians are fighting the government of President Goodluck Jonathan using Boko Haram as their agent because they do not want him to succeed. The attacks by Boko Haram have caused disorderliness in Nigeria and seriously affected the economy of the country.

2.6 ERADICATING CORRUPTION

Corrupt Nigerians do not truly understand the harm they are causing to other citizens. Corruption can be reduced by these possible remedies:

- Self-Satisfaction
- Institution of strong anti-corruption groups
- Employment generation
- Proper government funding of schools
- Treating all citizens equally

1. Self-Satisfaction

Self-Satisfaction in this context implies being content with what one has. When the leaders of Nigeria are satisfied with the salary they are paid and use them in the right way, the issue of embezzlement and money laundering will be history. Managers who are satisfied with what they are paid will not have time to indulge in corruption to make more money.

2. Institution of Strong Anti-Corruption Groups

Creating strong anti-corruption institutions is another arsenal to win the fight against corruption. This group is to work independently with the government to ensure transparency. Anyone who is caught in corrupt practice by the group should experience the consequences decided by the anti-corruption agency. That he is a minister or governor of a state should not be an excuse from facing the punishment he is to receive according to the Constitution of Nigeria.

3. Employment Generation

The unemployed in the country find themselves involved in corruption mainly because they want to make money to meet the demand of the day. Governments and capable hands should endeavour to generate more jobs for citizens to get employed and paid in return. A busy mind may find it difficult to indulge in corruption because he is being paid adequately.

4. Proper Government Funding of Schools

Understanding the importance of skill acquisition will go a long way to propel them to develop all the schools in Nigeria. When more attention is paid to the tertiary institutions in the country,

it will produce graduates who are employable. Installation of the necessary machines needed in universities will help Nigerian graduates acquire skills and use them to generate income, even if no company employs them after graduation.

Self-employment will make graduates more determined in the work they do and will prevent them from corruption like Internet scams, kidnapping and the rest.

5. Treating All Citizens Equally

Treating any offender in the country equally will help reduce corruption. Nobody is above the law and any who acts contrary to it should be given the punishment that he or she deserves. That she is the Minister of Aviation or Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria should not count in this case. If any minister or head of state is given the punishment he deserves for corruption, others will learn and separate themselves from any corrupt practice.

2.7 OTHER CAUSES OF BRAIN DRAIN

- i. Emigrants due to lack of employment and low salaries, and thus people are tempted to look for better salaries elsewhere - here, we talk about Economic factors.
- ii. The second cause of migration is political instability in home countries, thus they lose confidence to their government.
- iii. Migration taking place in response to wars, and political and social turmoil.
- iv. Leaving their family and workplace behind with the hope that a better life can be achieved elsewhere, despite their wellbeing at home those who seek asylum which deteriorates their lives and become `ashamed` of themselves to return home empty handed.
- v. Immigration flow due to lack of information and misguidance, are either tempted by significantly higher wages and better future prospects or give the blame to the political situation, which they say is a threat even for their lives.
- vi. Better working conditions.
- vii. Higher wages and income.
- viii. Unsatisfactory living conditions, lack of transport, housing, etc.
- ix. Under-utilization of qualified personnel; lack of satisfactory working conditions; low prospect of professional development.
- x. Lack of research and other facilities, including support staff; inadequacy of research funds, lack of professional equipment and tools.

2.8 THEEFFECTS OF BRAIN DRAIN

- a. Depleting its natural supply of intellectual talent.
- b. Losing thousands of their highly educated workers for the benefits of the rich countries and individuals themselves lent. And it is costing the continent \$4 billion dollars a year to replace them with expatriates from the West.
- c. Reduces the already low quantity of skilled manpower available in African countries and needed for their development.

- d. Reduces numbers of dynamic and innovative people, whether entrepreneurs or academics
Increases dependence on foreign technical assistance.
- e. Slows the transfer of technology and widens the gap between African and industrialized countries. Copied from: <http://baroudi.forumactif.org/t99-topic>

2.9 REVERTING THE TREND OF MIGRATION\BRAIN DRAIN

1. Educated Nigerians abroad (ENA) must start investing in Nigeria. Specifically, wealthy ENA should start building stores and industries in Nigeria. For instance, medical doctors should build some clinics and hospitals in Nigeria (staffed with their counterparts in Nigeria). Pharmacists should open up chemist stores in Nigeria (staffed with Nigerian pharmacists). Those in computer business should have computer training schools in Nigeria. Lawyers should have law offices in Nigeria. The list is endless. Investments in Nigeria will definitely create jobs; and the availability of jobs will definitely keep most Nigerian brains at home, and ultimately bring those abroad back to Nigeria for the collective task of nation-building.

2. It should be pointed out that not all investments in Nigeria require too much money. That is, most Nigerians abroad can invest in Nigeria no matter how small. For instance, some individuals can start saving money in Nigerian banks so that banks can lend out that money to businesses. It is a fact that banks and other financial institutions go bankrupt when they do not have money to lend out to businesses. And businesses, in turn, "go out of business" when they cannot borrow money from the banks and other financial institutions for their businesses. While this paper is not on banking and finance, it is prudent to note that banks and other financial institutions play a big role in any economy.

3. Equally important is the sponsorship of many talented and brilliant Nigerians in Nigerian universities. Sponsorship in Nigerian universities does not cost too much money, especially for Nigerians abroad. An average Nigerian abroad can sponsor up to five Nigerians in Nigerian universities without much sweat. Such sponsorship should go beyond immediate families, and reach out to those whose parents cannot afford to sponsor their children in universities. Some of us who are already doing that know the joy of such sponsorship.

4. In addition, Nigerian organizations abroad should constantly emphasize the importance of charity begins at home at every organizational conferences/meetings. All organizations should endeavor to address this question: What should we do to return to our country, Nigeria? In fact, Nigerian organizations can do a number of things: donating textbooks to the schools in their local government areas; establishing scholarship funds for talented and brilliant students in their towns; buying some hospital equipment for the hospitals in their localities, etc.

Nigerian leaders and elite at home should also do something to stop brain drain. This madness of rushing their money abroad (no matter how gotten) instead of investing it in Nigeria ONLY deprives Nigerian people green pasture. In fact, this charity begins abroad – caused by inferiority complex and lack of true education, the common sense -- is tantamount to slavery; it is self-enslavement, pure and simple. Just as slavery kept many Africans in poverty and perpetual servitude during the era of slavery, rushing Nigerian wealth abroad (by some Nigerians) is equally keeping many Nigerians in poverty and servitude. True education – the common sense—forbids leaders and the elite of any society from being a part of their own destruction.

And so, when Senator Newt Gingrich said on national TV (Sept. 26, 1998) that Americans should use their surpluses to lower their taxes instead of giving financial help to Bosnia and Africa, people like me got the Senator's message loud and clear: American charity should begin at home

(USA), not abroad (Bosnia or Africa). But the key question – and the greatest question of all time is whether African political and economic leaders in Africa will EVER get the message, and so act and react accordingly.

5. Establish necessary and positive political, social and economic conditions that would serve as incentives to curb the brain drain.

6. Better working conditions; develop and valorize Africa's human resources and create job and career opportunities.

7. Respect and consolidation of human rights and democracy, namely freedom of speech. 8. Establish necessary and positive political, social and economic conditions that would serve as incentives to curb the brain drain.

3.0 CONCLUSION

Brain drain has become a crucial part of the problems of development in Nigeria. Investment in Nigeria must be the central focus of all Nigerians wherever they are because investment is the ULTIMATE key for economic growth – the greener pasture/jobs. Availability of greener pasture in Nigeria will definitely retard brain drain and its concomitant problems of development in Nigeria.

4.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Federal government can also bring up the issue of brain drain at the United Nations. Any keen observer of international politics would know that the ‘super powers’ in the UN would make it look like a storm in the tea pot, the reason being that it is not in their interest to take the issue further in a very serious manner, thus offers rich opportunities to her citizens by making sure that her natural resources are tapped for development.

2. Our professionals abroad are worth more than any aids from the developed nations. It is high time our governments both federal and states took steps to encourage the reversal of brain drain which is terribly hurting our economy and the wellbeing of Nigeria. A whole generation and a variety of expertise are literally vaporizing from the surface called Nigeria. It would be too simplistic to see these professionals as unpatriotic rather the governments should address factors that facilitate their exodus from the country by ensuring political stability and freedom of the individual.

3. All Nigeria needs is cooperation from developed nations, we are abundantly blessed with both natural and human resources to the extent that we could transform our land to the best available anywhere in the world. Let the ordinary Nigerian be assured that he needs not be selfish in his dealings with fellow Nigerians and the nation, that the government would and could provide him with enabling environment and opportunities to develop his potentials.

4. In addition to setting up a national commission to look into it, Nigeria can use its influence with the leaders of the developed nations to bring the implications of brain drain for the developing nations to the international community-United Nations, European Union, and African Union etc starting from developing her industrial base for employment to take effect. These therefore, is the sure bet in the reduction of unemployment which is one of the factor to corruption which bring about instability in the Country cause migration, hence leading to brain drain amount to backwardness.

Simply put, the best indirect way of addressing the problem is the return of hope and a sense of having irreversible, increasingly responsible and humane government in Nigeria. This translates to selfless leadership with vision and mission.

Nigeria really has no alternative other than having governments and leaders that can demonstrably inspire in us the need to believe that our individual and collective hopes and aspirations can be achieved within the country.

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